

ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ПЕРЕБІГУ ВАГІТНОСТІ, ПОЛОГІВ, ТА ПІСЛЯПОЛОВОГО ПЕРІОДУ У ВАГІТНИХ З АЛОГЕННИМ ПЛОДОМ

CHARACTERISTICS OF PREGNANCY, CHILDBIRTH AND THE POSTPARTUM PERIOD IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH AN ALLOGENEIC FETUS

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Assisted reproductive technologies (ART) help to successfully overcome a number of aspects of such complex medical and social problems as infertility. In addition, the procedure of in vitro fertilization (IVF) using donor oocytes makes it possible to eliminate barriers caused by impaired gonadal development or premature loss of their function. However, it is known that patients enrolled in ART programs have an incidence of various obstetric and perinatal complications that differs from the general population, and both pathogenesis and actual rates are not yet known. It is obvious that the results of the use of ART with the formation of an allogeneic fetus are much less studied. The peculiarities of the fetoplacental complex functioning in such specific conditions and their impact on the incidence of obstetric and perinatal complications are not fully understood.

The aim of the study was to determine the characteristics of pregnancy, childbirth, and the postpartum period in women with an allogeneic fetus, and the factors that can affect it.

Materials and methods. Current scientific data on the features of interaction in the system "mother-placenta-fetus", as well as actual rates of obstetric and perinatal complications in pregnant women with allogeneic fetuses were analyzed.

Results and discussion. It has been established that one of the key roles in the pathogenesis of immune tolerance disorders during pregnancy with an allogeneic fetus is the mismatch of the fetal HLA epitope and the maternal inhibitory receptor variant expressed on natural killer cells, which can lead to increased rates of early pregnancy loss and obstetric complications, such as preeclampsia. It was also found that there is a significantly higher incidence of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy among women with allogeneic fetuses compared to the women undergoing IVF with their own oocytes. Statistically significant differences among other indicators of obstetric and perinatal complications, such as rates of premature birth, low birth weight, cesarean

section rates, and postpartum hemorrhage rates, were also noticed by several scientists. It has been established, however, that the impact of fetal allogeneity on the frequency of these complications has not been definitively clarified due to the presence of other risk factors in patients with these complications, in particular, multiple pregnancy. The research revealed substantial scientific data that prove the reduction of IVF success rates due to the influence of stress, as well as the presence of significant differences in the psychological status of women with an allogeneic fetus as compared to the rest of the pregnant women.

Conclusions. Increased rates of obstetric and perinatal complications have been repeatedly reported in pregnant women with an allogeneic fetus. Researchers also pointed out a significant impact of the psychological status of these women on the course of pregnancy, childbirth, and the postpartum period. Therefore, there is an obvious need to investigate the incidence of obstetric and perinatal complications in pregnant women with allogeneic fetuses and the possible ways to reduce their rates.

Keywords: assisted reproductive technologies (ART), in-vitro fertilization (IVF), allogeneic fetus, obstetric complications, perinatal outcomes, immune tolerance, fetoplacental complex, psychological status.

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